

RELEVANCE OF THE USE OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL ELECTRONIC TOOLS IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION IN IMPROVING STUDENT LITERACY AND INCREASING TEACHER POTENTIAL

Madmarova Feruzaxon

Student of Fergana State University

Ilhomjon Aldashev

Teacher of Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11118393>

Abstract: In the following article, as the field of education develops, the need for the use of new technologies increases, and the importance of the teacher applying the use of the latest modern electronic learning technologies to the classroom environment and the student's ability to quickly demonstrate new skills from this process is talked about.

Investing in education is the best investment, quality knowledge and equipment are essential to increase its quality, and it is not wrong to say that being aware of computer knowledge is the main task for people of the 21st century.

Key words: Interactive tools, virtual labs, multimedia, gamification, OER, visual simulations, personalized learning, traditional methods, game elements, massive open online courses, mobile learning apps, interactive whiteboards, presentation software.

The world of education is undergoing a dramatic transformation, driven by rapid technological advancements and evolving societal needs. Let's explore some key aspects of this change. Technologies are being unspearable peace of humankind as they have impackable functions that can provide everyone with their neccities. Today in each calling employees' whose are good aware of interactive technological tools and programmes reputation is higher than others. If this trend continues at the same speed as now it is ongoing, without a doubt after at least a decade people who are from 7 age to 70 years old will be good at using start-art-technologies over the globe. As it has a larger pool of advantages for 21 century's mankind, in terms of education both educator and learner are responsible for enhancing modern technological tools in the process of learning news that migh related to education or other fields. Using technology in education has become increasingly relevant for teachers and students alike. For teachers, technology provides tools for creating engaging lessons, assessing student progress, and personalizing learning experiences. It also enables collaboration and communication with students, parents, and colleagues. For students, technology offers access to a wealth of information, interactive learning materials, and opportunities for self-paced learning. It cultivates digital literacy skills and prepares students for the demands of the modern workforce. Overall, integrating technology in education enhances teaching and learning outcomes, fosters creativity, and promotes a more dynamic and inclusive educational environment.

Benefits for students

Engaging Learners with Technology: Interactive Tools, Multimedia, and Gamification.

Technology offers a wealth of opportunities to make learning more engaging and cater to diverse learning styles. Let's delve into how interactive tools, multimedia content, and gamification contribute to this:

Interactive Tools:

* **Active Participation:** Tools like virtual labs, simulations, and online quizzes allow students to actively participate in the learning process, moving beyond passive absorption of information. This hands-on experience fosters deeper understanding and retention.

* **Personalized Learning:** Adaptive learning platforms and interactive exercises can adjust to individual student needs and pace, providing personalized learning paths. This addresses diverse learning styles and ensures everyone can progress at their own speed.

* **Collaboration and Communication:** Online collaboration tools facilitate group projects, discussions, and peer feedback, promoting teamwork and communication skills. This creates a more dynamic and interactive learning environment.

Multimedia Content:

* **Visual and Auditory Stimulation:** Integrating videos, images, audio clips, and infographics caters to different learning preferences and makes learning more stimulating and accessible. Visual learners benefit from images and videos, while auditory learners grasp concepts better through audio explanations and podcasts.

* **Real-World Connections:** Multimedia content brings real-world examples and scenarios into the classroom, making learning more relevant and relatable. This helps students connect abstract concepts to tangible applications.

* **Enhanced Comprehension:** Combining text with visuals and audio explanations strengthens understanding and memory recall. Students can visualize complex ideas and processes, improving overall comprehension.

Gamification:

* **Motivation and Engagement:** Game elements like points, badges, leaderboards, and challenges introduce a sense of competition and achievement, motivating students to actively participate and progress. This can be particularly helpful for students who struggle with traditional learning methods.

* **Immediate Feedback:** Gamified learning platforms provide instant feedback, allowing students to gauge their understanding and adjust their strategies accordingly. This immediate feedback loop encourages self-reflection and improvement.

* **Fun and Enjoyment:** Gamification injects fun and playfulness into the learning process, making it more enjoyable and reducing anxiety associated with academic tasks. This creates a positive learning environment where students are eager to participate.

Catering to Diverse Learning Styles:

The combination of interactive tools, multimedia content, and gamification creates a diverse learning environment that caters to various learning styles. Visual learners benefit from engaging visuals, auditory learners appreciate audio explanations, and kinesthetic learners enjoy the interactive nature of simulations and games. This allows each student to learn in a way that best suits their individual preferences and strengths.

In one word, technology empowers educators to create engaging and inclusive learning experiences that cater to diverse learning styles. Interactive tools, multimedia content, and gamification promote active participation, personalize learning paths, and motivate students to reach their full potential.

Expanding Educational Horizons: Accessibility and Flexibility through Technology

Technology plays a crucial role in breaking down geographical barriers and making education more accessible and flexible. Let's explore how online learning platforms, open educational resources (OERs), and mobile learning apps contribute to this:

Online Learning Platforms:

- * **Global Reach:** Online platforms like MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) and virtual universities offer courses and programs to learners worldwide, regardless of location. This expands access to quality education for individuals in remote areas or those with limited mobility.
- * **Diverse Course Offerings:** These platforms provide a vast array of courses across various disciplines, catering to diverse interests and career aspirations. Learners can pursue specific skills or explore new areas of knowledge, broadening their educational horizons.
- * **Flexible Learning Schedules:** Online platforms often offer asynchronous learning options, allowing students to access materials and complete assignments at their own pace and convenience. This flexibility is especially beneficial for working professionals, parents, or individuals with busy schedules.

Open Educational Resources (OERs):

- * **Free and Accessible Learning Materials:** OERs encompass a wide range of freely accessible educational materials, including textbooks, lecture notes, videos, and interactive simulations. This removes financial barriers to education and empowers learners to access quality resources without cost constraints.
- * **Customization and Adaptability:** OERs can be adapted and modified to suit specific learning needs and contexts. Educators can tailor materials to align with their curriculum or create personalized learning experiences for their students.
- * **Community Collaboration:** OER repositories foster collaboration and knowledge sharing among educators and learners worldwide. This collective effort contributes to the continuous improvement and diversification of educational resources.

Mobile Learning Apps:

- * **Learning on the Go:** Mobile apps enable learners to access educational content and complete learning activities anytime, anywhere. This portability and convenience make learning more accessible and adaptable to individual lifestyles.
- * **Microlearning Opportunities:** Many apps offer bite-sized learning modules and activities, facilitating microlearning experiences that fit into short breaks or commutes. This approach enhances knowledge retention and accommodates busy schedules.
- * **Personalized Learning Support:** Some mobile apps incorporate AI-powered features that personalize learning pathways, provide adaptive feedback, and offer targeted support based on individual progress and learning needs.

Overall, technology-driven solutions like online learning platforms, OERs, and mobile learning apps play a transformative role in democratizing education. They provide flexible learning options, remove geographical and financial barriers, and empower learners worldwide to access quality educational resources and pursue their educational goals.

Benefits for educators

Transforming Instruction Delivery: Technology in the Classroom.

Technology tools like interactive whiteboards, presentation software, and learning management systems (LMS) have revolutionized instruction delivery, fostering a more engaging and interactive learning environment. Let's explore how each of these tools contributes:

Interactive Whiteboards:

- * **Dynamic Presentations:** Interactive whiteboards transform static presentations into dynamic, engaging experiences. Educators can annotate content, highlight key points, and incorporate multimedia elements to capture students' attention and enhance understanding.
- * **Collaboration and Participation:** These boards encourage active participation by allowing students to interact directly with the content. They can write, draw, or manipulate objects on the board, promoting collaboration and hands-on learning experiences.
- * **Visualization and Demonstration:** Interactive whiteboards excel at visualizing complex concepts and processes. Educators can use them to demonstrate scientific experiments, solve math problems, or illustrate historical events, making abstract ideas more tangible and easier to grasp.

Presentation Software:

- * **Visual Storytelling:** Presentation software enables educators to create visually appealing presentations that incorporate images, videos, and animations. This visual storytelling approach enhances engagement and helps students connect with the material on a deeper level.
- * **Organized and Structured Content:** Presentations provide a structured framework for delivering information, ensuring clear and concise communication of key concepts. This helps students follow the flow of ideas and retain information more effectively.
- * **Accessibility and Sharing:** Presentation files can be easily shared with students, allowing them to review material at their own pace and revisit key points. This promotes independent learning and reinforces understanding.

Learning Management Systems (LMS):

- * **Centralized Learning Hub:** LMS platforms serve as a centralized hub for course materials, assignments, and communication. Students can access resources, submit assignments, and participate in discussions, all within a single platform. This streamlines the learning process and promotes organization.
- * **Personalized Learning Paths:** Many LMS platforms offer features that allow educators to personalize learning experiences. They can create differentiated assignments, track individual progress, and provide targeted feedback, catering to diverse learning needs and paces.
- * **Communication and Collaboration:** LMS platforms facilitate communication between students and teachers through discussion forums, messaging systems, and announcements. This fosters collaboration, encourages active participation, and allows for timely feedback and support.

Overall, these technological tools empower educators to deliver instruction in a more engaging, interactive, and personalized manner. They promote active learning, enhance understanding, and facilitate communication and collaboration between teachers and students, contributing to a more effective and dynamic learning environment.

References:

1. Akhmedov, B. A., Majidov, J. M., Narimbetova, Z. A., Kuralov, Yu. A. (2020). Active interactive and distance forms of the cluster method of learning in development of higher education. Экономика и социум, 12(79), 805-808.
2. www.weareconker.uz
3. www.information-age.com
4. www.cyberlininka.ru

